

Effects of Aqueous Extract of *Ipomoea batatas* (Sweet Potato) Leaves on the Frontal Cortex of Diabetic Wistar Rats

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Abstract

Background: Diabetes mellitus represents a significant public health concern worldwide, with Sub-Saharan Africa—including Zambia—facing a growing burden. The condition has been associated with cognitive impairments and alterations in brain structure. Sweet potato leaves, known for their antioxidant properties, have been traditionally used in the management of various ailments, including diabetes. This study aimed to evaluate the impact of aqueous sweet potato leaf extract on the frontal cortex of diabetic Wistar rats.

Materials and Methods: A total of thirty-six adult male Wistar rats were allocated into six experimental groups: normal control, sweet potato leaf extract only, diabetic + sweet potato leaf extract, diabetic + insulin, diabetic + metformin, and diabetic only. Diabetes was induced using streptozotocin at a dose of 70 mg/kg body weight. Treatments commenced 72 hours after induction and continued for four weeks. The administered doses were: sweet potato leaf extract (700 mg/kg), metformin (100 mg/kg), and insulin (4 IU/kg).

Results: Compared to the untreated diabetic group, animals in the diabetic + sweet potato leaf extract, diabetic + insulin, and diabetic + metformin groups showed statistically significant improvements in body weight and relative brain weight ($p < 0.05$). Normoglycemia was achieved by the third week in the group receiving sweet potato leaf extract, while insulin and metformin groups reached similar levels by week four. Glucose metabolism enzymes and oxidative stress biomarkers exhibited differential activity, with more favorable outcomes in the treatment groups. Histological evaluation revealed evidence of neuroprotection among treated animals.

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Conclusion: The results suggest that sweet potato leaf extract possesses neuroprotective effects and may serve as a potential intervention to mitigate diabetes-induced cognitive dysfunction.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus, a chronic metabolic disorder, is a global epidemic affecting millions [1]. In Sub-Saharan Africa, it affects 6% of the population, with Zambia experiencing a significant burden of 7.2%, affecting 7.2% of the population [2]. Diabetes mellitus has significant health impacts, including cardiovascular diseases, kidney dysfunction, retinopathy, and neuropathy [3-4]. It's also linked to cognitive impairment. Traditional treatments include pharmaceuticals, lifestyle modifications, and dietary controls [5]. However, there's growing interest in natural extracts, like sweet potato leaves, for potential therapeutic benefits [6].

Sweet potato leaves, a byproduct of sweet potato cultivation, contain bioactive compounds like antioxidants and anti-inflammatory agents, which may help address diabetes-related mechanisms like oxidative stress and inflammation [7]. The frontal cortex, crucial for executive functions, may be affected by diabetes, potentially leading to cognitive deficits, but precise mechanisms and interventions remain elusive [8].

Thus, a significant knowledge gap exists concerning the impact of Diabetes mellitus on the frontal cortex and, subsequently, the potential role of sweet potato leaf extract in influencing frontal cortex changes. Understanding how sweet potato leaf extract could potentially influence the frontal cortex in diabetic conditions is a critical aspect of this research.

Methods and Materials

Plant Material

Sweet potato leaves were sourced from Sikobo Farm in Zambia and authenticated at the School of Natural Sciences, University of Zambia. The leaves were air-dried, crushed, pulverized, and sifted to obtain a fine powder. Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry was then used for extraction, resulting in a uniform preparation [9].

Animal Model and Housing

This research was conducted using 36 healthy male Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus*), aged between 8 and 10 weeks, with body weights ranging from 160 to 200 grams. The animals were housed in six separate cages at the Department of Anatomy, Mulungushi University School of Medicine and Health Sciences, and maintained under standard conditions with access to regular feed and clean water.

Diabetes Induction Protocol

Following an overnight fast, baseline blood glucose levels were measured, and diabetes was induced via intraperitoneal injection of streptozotocin (STZ) at 70

mg/kg body weight. Seventy-two hours post-injection, animals were tested using a tail vein blood sample, and those exhibiting glucose levels above 7 mmol/L or ≥ 250 mg/dL were confirmed diabetic (glucometer: Accu-Chek Compact Plus, USA) [10,11].

Experimental Grouping

The rats were randomly distributed into six groups (n=6 per group) as follows:

- Group I: Normal control
- Group II: Sweet potato leaf extract only
- Group III: Diabetic + Sweet potato leaf extract
- Group IV: Diabetic + Insulin
- Group V: Diabetic + Metformin
- Group VI: Diabetic control

Administration of Sweet Potato Extract

Sweet potato leaf powder was dissolved daily in physiological saline and administered orally to rats in Groups II and III via oro-gastric cannula at a dose of 700 mg/kg body weight between 9:00–10:00 AM for four weeks. Group IV received insulin at 4 IU/kg/day, while Group V was treated with metformin at 100 mg/kg/day [12–14]. Groups I and VI were given 2 ml of physiological saline daily for the same duration.

Blood Glucose Monitoring

Fasting blood glucose levels were assessed between 9:00 and 10:00 AM using the glucose oxidase method (One Touch Ultra 2, Accu-Chek Compact Plus). Blood samples were collected weekly via a tail prick from the median caudal vein, starting from the two-week acclimatization phase through to the four-week treatment period [11].

Body Weight Assessment

Body weights of all rats were measured using a Venus VT 30 SL digital scale during the two weeks prior to diabetes induction and then weekly throughout the treatment period [11].

Relative Brain Weight Calculation

The relative brain weight was determined as a percentage of the brain weight relative to the terminal body weight using a precision balance (Sony F3G model) [15].

Histological and Biochemical Analysis

At the conclusion of the study, animals were euthanized, and the brain tissues were carefully excised. Samples for histology were fixed in freshly prepared formal saline for 72 hours, processed, and stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E). Additional staining techniques such as phosphotungstic acid hematoxylin (PTAH) and cresyl violet were also used to highlight specific histological features. Tissue samples designated for enzymatic (G6PDH, LDH) and oxidative

stress marker (GSH, SOD) analyses were homogenized in 0.1M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4).

Photomicrography

Images of histological sections of the frontal cortex were captured using an Olympus microscope with an attached digital camera at the Department of Human Anatomy, Mulungushi University School of Medicine and Health Sciences, Livingstone Campus, Zambia.

Statistical Evaluation

All data were presented as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM). Statistical significance was determined using one-way ANOVA, and all graphical representations were prepared using Microsoft Excel. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Figure 1 illustrates the weekly average body weight changes across the study groups. During the acclimatization period (weeks -2 and -1), no statistically significant differences were observed in body weights among the groups ($p > 0.05$). From week 0 to week 1, body weights remained relatively stable across all groups, with no significant changes ($p > 0.05$). However, between weeks 2 and 4, the diabetic control group showed a notable reduction in body weight compared to other groups, which was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Meanwhile, rats treated with sweet potato leaf extract, insulin, or metformin exhibited stable body weights comparable to both the normal control and the extract-only groups, with no significant differences ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 1: Average Body weight (g) on Weekly Basis. Data were Analyzed Using Mean ± SEM and $p < 0.05$ Considered Significant

Figure 2: Relative Organ Weight. Data were Analyzed Using Mean ± SEM and $p < 0.05$ Considered Significant

Figure 2 illustrates the relative weight of the brain in the different groups of rats. The diabetic group showed a significant decrease in relative brain weight when compared to other groups it was significant ($p < 0.05$). The rats in the diabetic + aqueous sweet potatoes leaves extract, diabetic+metformin and diabetic+insulin showed slight decline, when compared to control and aqueous sweet potatoes leaves extract only they were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$).

Histochemical Study of the Frontal Cortex

Frontal cortex of glucose 6 phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PDH) activity level (IU/L) in the frontal cortex

Figure 3 illustrates the levels of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PDH) activity in the frontal cortex across different groups of Wistar rats. Among all groups, the rats treated with aqueous sweet potato leaf extract demonstrated the highest G6PDH activity, whereas the diabetic control group recorded the lowest. The differences between these groups were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). However, the groups receiving diabetic treatments—either with sweet potato extract, insulin, or metformin—showed

comparable enzyme activity levels to those of the control and extract-only groups, with no significant variation ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 3: Frontal Cortex of Glucose 6 Phosphate Dehydrogenase (G6PDH) Activity Level (IU/L) at the End of Fourth Week
Data are Expressed as Mean±SEM. $P < 0.05$

Figure 4: Frontal Cortex of Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH) Activity Level (IU/L) at the End of Fourth Week.
Data are Expressed as Mean±SEM. $p < 0.05$

Frontal cortex of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity level (IU/L) in the frontal cortex

Figure 4 presents lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity in the frontal cortex across the experimental groups. The diabetic group showed significantly elevated LDH activity compared to all other groups ($p < 0.05$). However, LDH levels in the diabetic groups treated with sweet potato extract, insulin, or metformin did not differ significantly from the control or extract-only groups ($p > 0.05$).

Frontal cortex of reduced glutathione (GSH) activity level (IU/L) in the frontal cortex

Figure 5 displays the concentration of reduced glutathione (GSH) in the frontal cortex of the experimental animals. The diabetic control group exhibited the lowest GSH levels, while the extract-only group had the highest. The difference in GSH activity between the diabetic group and other groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Nonetheless, no significant differences in GSH levels were observed between the treated diabetic groups (sweet potato extract, insulin, metformin) and the control or extract-only groups ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 5: Frontal Cortex of Glutathione (GSH) Activity Level (IU/L) at the End of Fourth Week. Data are Expressed as Mean±SEM. $p < 0.05$

Frontal cortex of Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity level (IU/L) in the frontal cortex

Figure 6 shows the activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD) in the various rat groups. Both the control and sweet potato leaf extract-only groups demonstrated significantly higher SOD activity compared to the diabetic group ($p < 0.05$). The diabetic groups treated with extract, insulin, or metformin showed SOD activity levels similar to the control and extract-only groups, and these differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Histological Findings

Haematoxylin and eosin stain of Frontal cortex

Figure 7 displays histological sections of the frontal cortex. The control and extract-only groups exhibited well-preserved histoarchitecture and numerous healthy pyramidal neurons (Figures 7A and 7B). In contrast, the diabetic rats treated with sweet potato extract, insulin, or metformin showed a mix of normal and necrotic neurons (Figures 7C, 7D, and 7E). The untreated diabetic group had predominantly necrotic cells (Figure 7F).

Figure 6: Frontal Cortex of Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) Activity Level (IU/L) at the End of Fourth Week. Data are Expressed as Mean±SEM. P<0.05

Figure 7: Photomicrograph Showing the Frontal Cortex at Day 28. H&E stain X400. A- Normal control, B – Sweet Potato Leaves only, C – Diabetic+ Sweet Potato Leaves, D – Diabetic+Insulin E- Diabetic Metformin and F- Diabetic only. Arrow – Pyramidal cells, arrow head is necrotic cells

Toluidine blue stain of Frontal cortex

Figure 8 demonstrates Nissl staining results. Control and sweet potato extract-only groups showed clearly stained Nissl substances and intact pyramidal cells

(Figures 8A and 8B). In treated diabetic groups (sweet potato extract, insulin, and metformin), Nissl substance was preserved in some neurons, though others showed necrosis (Figures 8C, 8D, and 8E). In the diabetic control

group, most neurons appeared necrotic, and Nissl staining was weak or sparse (Figure 8F).

Figure 8: Photomicrograph Showing the Frontal Cortex at Day 28. TDB stain X400. A- Normal control, B – Sweet Potato Leaves only, C – Diabetic+ Sweet Potato Leaves, D – Diabetic+Insulin E- Diabetic+Metformin and F- Diabetic only. Arrow – Pyramidal cells, arrow head is necrotic cells

Silver stain of Frontal cortex

Figure 9 illustrates axonal integrity. The control and extract-only groups displayed structurally normal axons without signs of axonal reaction (Figures 9A and 9B). Rats in the diabetic + sweet potato extract group showed no signs of axonal damage (Figure 9C). In

contrast, diabetic rats treated with insulin or metformin exhibited a mix of normal and degenerating axons (Figures 9C, 9D, and 9E). Most axons in the untreated diabetic group exhibited clear signs of axonal degeneration (Figure 9F).

Figure 9: Photomicrograph Showing the Frontal Cortex at Day 28. Silver stain X400. A- Normal control, B – Sweet Potato Leaves only, C – Diabetic+ Sweet Potato Leaves, D – Diabetic+Insulin E- Diabetic+Metformin and F- Diabetic only. Arrow – Axon, arrow head is axonal reaction

Discussion

Sweet potato leaves and their constituent polyphenols have been associated with anti-hyperglycemic properties, antioxidant activity, enhancement of cerebral circulation, cognitive improvement, and neurogenesis. These attributes justify their traditional use in managing diabetes [16,17].

In the present study, rats in the diabetic-only group exhibited a significant reduction in average body weight from the second to the fourth week, a trend consistent with gluconeogenesis-related weight loss as previously documented [18,19]. On the other hand, the diabetic groups treated with aqueous sweet potato leaf extract, insulin, or metformin maintained stable body weights, comparable to the normal control group. This stabilization is possibly due to the inhibition of gluconeogenesis by these interventions [20]. The marked weight loss in the untreated diabetic group likely resulted from insulin deficiency, which disrupted energy metabolism, prompting the breakdown of muscle and fat through glycolysis to meet energy demands [18,19]. Both insulin and metformin are known to suppress gluconeogenesis by inhibiting enzymes like glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase [20]. The aqueous extract of sweet potato leaves contains bioactive components, such as flavonoids and saponins, which may assist in glycemic control through mechanisms like insulin release stimulation, beta-cell regeneration, gluconeogenesis suppression, and adipogenesis prevention [21,22]. The findings by [19] and [20] further support the outcomes observed in this study.

Moreover, the diabetic-only group demonstrated a significant decline in relative brain weight when compared to other experimental groups. This decline may be attributed to neural cell loss caused by inflammation, oxidative stress, and impaired cerebral perfusion [23]. Conversely, the diabetic groups treated with sweet potato leaf extract, insulin, or metformin maintained brain weights similar to the control, suggesting a protective effect against hyperglycemia-induced neuronal damage [24]. The presence of flavonoids in the sweet potato leaves may explain this outcome, as these compounds are known to decrease malondialdehyde (MDA) and enhance the expression of antioxidant genes such as SOD2, offering neuroprotection [25]. Metformin's neuroprotective effects have also been linked to increased expression of Growth/Differentiation Factor 15 (GDF15), which plays a role in weight regulation and insulin balance [26]. Insulin has similarly been shown to mitigate cognitive and hippocampal damage in diabetic models [27], supporting the mechanisms through which these treatments preserve brain structure and function.

In terms of glycemic control, the diabetic-only group showed markedly elevated blood glucose levels, likely due to the beta-cell cytotoxicity induced by streptozotocin, resulting in inadequate insulin secretion, as explained by [28]. Notably, normoglycemia was achieved by week 3 in the group treated with sweet potato leaf extract, while insulin- and metformin-treated groups attained it by week 4. This hypoglycemic effect of sweet potato leaves may stem from their polyphenolic constituents, including flavonoids, tannins, phenolic acids, and lignans [29]. These compounds may enhance glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) secretion and hexokinase activity, which collectively promote insulin release and inhibit gluconeogenesis [29–31]. Insulin replacement therapy facilitates glucose uptake via GLUT4 translocation [32], while metformin enhances insulin sensitivity by increasing cAMP, improving cellular glucose uptake [33]. These results correspond with those of Chun-[34], who observed similar effects using white sweet potato leaf extracts.

The current findings also reveal a substantial decline in glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PDH) activity in the diabetic-only group relative to the others. This reduction may be attributed to suppressed gene expression and elevated phosphorylation of G6PD, which lead to oxidative stress and pancreatic beta-cell apoptosis [35,36]. By contrast, the diabetic groups receiving sweet potato leaf extract, insulin, or metformin exhibited G6PDH activity akin to that of the control group. The antioxidant-rich nature of sweet potato leaves, particularly their phenolic acid content, likely enhances G6PDH activity by neutralizing reactive oxygen species [37]. Although the precise mechanisms remain unclear, both insulin and metformin appear to support G6PDH activity restoration, further contributing to oxidative stress reduction [38].

Elevated lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity was observed in the diabetic-only group, suggesting metabolic stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, and heightened anaerobic glycolysis under oxidative conditions [39,40]. In contrast, treatment with sweet potato leaf extract, insulin, or metformin mitigated LDH activity. The polyphenols in sweet potato leaves likely attenuate oxidative damage and support mitochondrial health, resulting in normalized LDH levels [41]. Insulin reduces glucose-induced metabolic stress, and metformin improves metabolic function by enhancing insulin sensitivity and lowering hepatic glucose output [42–44]. These observations align with findings from [39] and [41].

Regarding antioxidant defense, the diabetic-only group exhibited the lowest reduced glutathione (GSH) levels, which is indicative of oxidative stress surpassing cellular antioxidant capacity [45]. The groups treated with

sweet potato leaf extract, insulin, or metformin maintained higher GSH levels. This improvement can be attributed to the antioxidant compounds in sweet potato leaves, especially flavonoids and polyphenols, which help restore redox balance and prevent neural tissue damage [46]. These findings corroborate the work of [47]. While insulin regulates glycemia and metformin enhances insulin action and reduces hepatic glucose production, both contribute indirectly to reducing oxidative damage [38,48].

A similar pattern was observed with superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity: the diabetic-only group had the lowest SOD levels, reflecting impaired antioxidant defense mechanisms under hyperglycemia-induced oxidative stress [49]. The diabetic + sweet potato leaves extract, insulin, and metformin groups showed SOD activity comparable to that of the control, likely due to the protective effects of antioxidants in sweet potato leaves [50]. These bioactive compounds enhance endogenous antioxidant systems, supporting cellular resilience [50]. Insulin and metformin contribute to this effect by mitigating hyperglycemia and its associated ROS production [50]. These findings are in line with the results reported by [50].

Histological analysis using hematoxylin and eosin staining revealed extensive neuronal necrosis in the diabetic-only group, while other treatment groups exhibited relatively preserved cortical architecture with fewer necrotic cells. These differences are attributable to the antioxidant effects of flavonoids in sweet potato leaves, which counter oxidative stress and neuronal damage [51,52]. Metformin and insulin therapies were also effective in reducing hyperglycemia-driven neuronal degeneration, as demonstrated by [53].

Toluidine blue staining of the frontal cortex indicated reduced Nissl substance and widespread necrosis in the diabetic-only group, consistent with oxidative stress-induced neuronal damage [51]. In contrast, the diabetic + sweet potato leaves, insulin, and metformin groups showed well-preserved Nissl bodies, indicating better neuronal integrity. These outcomes are associated with the combined effects of glycemic control and antioxidant action from the treatments used [54–55]. Metformin, through its insulin-sensitizing and antioxidant effects, helps in preserving neuronal structure [44].

Finally, silver staining revealed significant axonal degeneration in the diabetic-only group, attributed to chronic hyperglycemia and ROS accumulation [56]. The absence of axonal damage in the sweet potato leaves-treated group suggests robust antioxidant protection and improved glycemic regulation [30]. Insulin and metformin treatments partially mitigated axonal damage, reflecting their roles in modulating oxidative stress and preserving neuronal function [44,55,57].

These findings are consistent with [5], who discussed therapeutic strategies for diabetic neuropathy.

Conclusion

The sweet potatoes aqueous leaves aqueous extract exhibit substantial neuroprotective characteristics, effectively counteracting the harmful impact of diabetes on the frontal cortex by reversing anti-diabetic effect reducing oxidative stress, protecting neuronal structure, and preserving axonal integrity.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts interest.

Funding

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Ethical Considerations

Before commencement of the study ethical approval was obtained from Mulungushi University School of Medicine and Health Sciences ethics committee and National Health Research Authority-Zambia.

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